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THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL PRESS IN TURKESTAN AND JADIDISM

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ABSTRACT.

In this article, the efforts aimed at the formation of the national press by the bright representatives of the Jadidist movement, which operated in Turkestan in the late 19th - early 20th centuries, and their journalistic works against the background of the political and social problems of their time have been thoroughly reviewed.

Key words: *struggle, national press, newspaper, magazine, article, propaganda field.*

In the early 20th century, the Jadids of Turkestan were involved not only in artistic creation, scientific activity, and reforming schools and education, but also in the formation of national press. On the one hand, the forces that nourished the Uzbek Jadid movement were the great scholars and thinkers who had lived in the nation's past. By studying their spiritual and intellectual heritage, the Jadids learned how high their people had reached. It is a well-known truth that the Jadids also sought to know the spiritual values of the past and work towards reforming its problematic aspects. To carry out reforms, it was necessary to define the significance of each piece of cultural heritage in its own time and in the present, determine its relevance to the future, and convey it in unique forms for the national uplift of the people.

The renowned scholar of literary criticism, H. Boltaboyev, writes the following about this: "Jadidism, which entered the history of Turkestan as the author of monumental changes, left a significant mark not only in Central Asia but also in Eurasia. As a result, it is being studied attentively by global academic thought... Jadidism, while promoting the slogan of seeing its people free and its homeland

prosperous, also had the supreme and ultimate goal of introducing the nation's glorious history and culture to the world's intellectual community. For this reason, the strikes of Timur's sword, which shook the world, and the pen of Navoi, which created a new chapter in world literature, became symbols of the era for the Jadids. Understanding well that idealizing the past would not lead to the creation of a new and elevated society, the Jadids sought not only to assimilate the past heritage but also to see themselves as part of the world's most advanced nations. However, the tree that sprouted from these roots had to go through a difficult path, reaching towards the sun, growing the buds of faith, national consciousness, and independence, and it sacrificed many lives along the way."

The Jadid movement in Turkestan also sought to make use of the opportunities provided by the railway, printing press, and media, which came with the Russian conquest. Despite significant resistance from the Russian authorities, articles by Uzbek poets and intellectuals, such as Furqat and Sattorxon, were regularly published in the "Turkiston viloyatining gazeti" (The Turkestan Province Newspaper), which was a Turkish-language supplement to the "Turkestarskie vedomosti" (Turkestan Gazette) (as described by N. Ostroumov, "sartcha" – a term for Turkic language).

In several of Sattorxon's works, his thoughts on various issues, such as judicial and state structures, corruption, regionalism, and eliminating internal conflicts, remain valuable even today. Sattorxon emerged as one of the first promoters of Russian science and culture. In one of his articles published in the "Turkiston viloyatining gazeti" (on May 14, 1890), he wrote: "Through the help of the Russian people, we can establish connections with the European nations, and as a result, we will become participants in the global life and scientific progress."

N. Ostroumov, who served as the editor of the "Turkiston viloyatining gazeti" for thirty-five years, also paid significant attention to promoting Russian and European culture and way of life. His newspaper regularly published travelogues of Uzbek merchants and intellectuals who had traveled to Russia and Europe.

For example, the impressions of Samarkand merchant Mirza Bukhari, who participated in the agricultural exhibition held in Kharkov in 1887, from his visits to Baku, Kharkov, Moscow, and St. Petersburg (issues 4-7 in 1888), the journey of Tashkent merchant Tojimuhammad Isamukhamedov to Paris via Baku-Istanbul in 1900 (issues 44-45), travel notes and memoirs of newspaper editors such as Sattorxon Abdug'afforov (1893), poet Zokirjon Furqat (issues 22-28, 32 in 1891), Khudoyorkhon's younger son Ibn Yaminbek (issue 20 in 1893), and Tashkent merchant Orifxojan (issue 28 in 1894) were published in the pages of the newspaper.

On June 27, 1906, the first Jadid press in Turkestan, the "Taraqiy" newspaper (edited by Ismoil Obidiy), was launched. On September 6, a group of Jadids led by

Munavvar Qori began publishing the "Xurshid" newspaper. After the 10th issue was published, the newspaper was shut down by the government. In 1907, Abdulla Avloni's "Shuhrat" newspaper began its publication. In 1912, the "Buxoroi Sharif" newspaper started being published in Bukhara. This newspaper, which began in Persian, not in the Turkic language of the native people of Central Asia, but in Persian (which Navoi called "Sart language"), made some Turkic scholars abroad, as well as the people of Turkestan, ponder. The "Turk Yurdi" journal, surprised by this situation, dedicated a special article to it, as noted in the research of Japanese scholar Professor Hisao Komatsun.

It is likely that these criticisms led to the introduction of a weekly "Turon" supplement in Uzbek for the newspaper. In April 1913, the "Samarqand" newspaper was launched, with Mufti Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy appointed as the responsible editor. The newspaper, which published articles in Uzbek, Persian, and Russian, featured works by Jadid intellectuals such as Mirzohid Miroqilov, Akobir Mansur, and Hoji Muin. With a circulation of nearly six hundred copies, the newspaper published 45 issues before closing due to a lack of funds. Starting from August 20, 1913, Behbudiy began publishing his own journal, "Oyina." The journal featured several articles by Munavvar Qori, Mahmud Sattor, and Akobir Mansur, and carried the slogan "Nation, Islamic prosperity." However, "Oyina" also closed after publishing its 136th issue on June 15, 1915.

Another significant publication, "Sadoi Turkiston," began in 1914 and left a lasting mark on the history of Jadidism. Its editor-in-chief was Ubaydullaxo'ja Asatillaxo'jaev, and the newspaper received close support from Munavvar Qori and Abduraufzoda. "Sadoi Farg'ona," which was published almost simultaneously, was edited by Obidjon Mahmudiy. Professor B. Qosimov, reflecting on the newspapers published after the February 1917 events, wrote that after February 1917, many newspapers were launched, such as "Najot" (Munavvar Qori), "Sho'roi Islom" (A. Battol), "Turon" (Avloni), "Hurriyat" (Fitrat), "Kengash" (Zaki Validiy), "El Bayrog'i" (B. Soliev, A. Zohiriy), and "Ulug' Turkiston" (K. Bakir). Among these, the "Hurriyat" newspaper, published in Samarkand, featured hundreds, even thousands, of articles, news pieces, poems, and stories, which served as one of the main factors in the development of Jadid literature and confirmed the claim of the importance of Jadid press. Articles and research about the history of Turkestan's Jadid press also emerged. Initially, Cho'lpon published an article titled "Matbuot in Turkestan." Later, Abdulla Avloni summarized the publications from 1905-1917 in his article "The History of the Early Uzbek Periodical Press." Ten years later, Ziyoy Said's famous book "Materials on the History of Uzbek Periodical Press (1870-1927)" was published.

Looking at the history of Jadid press, it is clear that the publications carried out by the Jadids contributed to the awakening of the nation, and secondly, almost all the leaders of the Jadid movement actively participated in press work and found effective methods and ways to ensure that their articles and literary works reached the public.

In the 1920 publication "Fuqaro Fuyuzato" in Baku, in the article titled "Matbuot in Turkestan," Cho'lpon provided the following assessment of the local press, its role in public life, and its place in political reality: "In the past, it was said: 'The press is the seventh power.' This statement, this claim, has not lost its significance. Even today, the importance of the press remains great. Particularly, the people of the East have now understood the significance of the press. It has awakened the Eastern people who were unaware of the great revolutionary movements of the world, filling their bloodless veins with the sacred blood of struggle, 'to fight for life.' The press is now sought, found, and discussed by the Easterners, who are confined in prisons, by foreign people with special 'shay' (propaganda), who study and reflect upon it. These people, who look at the world and even the life of their cities with a keen eye, are determined to learn about the grand, combative, and relevant life far from their own land."

Alongside Cho'lpon's article, the publication of his poem "Sharq isyoni" ("East Uprising") in the Azerbaijani press is related to the historical congress of Eastern peoples held in Baku in early September 1920. It is known that Cho'lpon participated in this congress as part of a delegation from Turkestan. Cho'lpon's article "Matbuot in Turkestan," being one of the earliest works on this subject, is significant not only for its date of writing but also for its fair and impartial evaluation of how the newspapers and journals published during the period of Soviet rule served the nation. It holds value as a fair and honest assessment of the role that press publications played in serving the nation at that time.

By this time, Muslim printing presses (bookprinting) began to operate in Tashkent and Bukhara. In Tashkent, wealthy individuals such as Fulom Hasan Orifjonov started printing a number of works in Persian and Uzbek languages using the lithography method at his printing press. The Porsov printing press in Tashkent and the Livnin printing press in Bukhara published a series of works related to history and literature, including Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa," Ahmad Yassavi's "Divan," "Abo Muslim's Tales," "Temurnama," and "Shahnameh." In Tashkent, a publishing company named "Turkiston" was also established for the purpose of publishing new works.

In short, at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the prominent representatives of the Jadid movement in Turkestan made significant contributions to the formation of national press, which became a wide platform for the promotion of their ideas.

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